

THE PREPARATION OF THE PEDAGOGICAL PROJECT, UNDERSTOOD AS THE RESPECTIVE SYSTEMATICS OF THE PEDAGOGICAL WORK OF THE SCHOOL, AND ITS PARTNERS

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ABSTRACT

The Pedagogical Project (PP) of the school is an essential instrument for directing and articulating educational actions, ensuring coherence in pedagogical work. More than a normative document, it guides school practices in an integrated manner, aligning them with the socio-historical context and reflecting the institution's values and objectives. Its construction must be participatory, involving educators, students, and other members of the school community, ensuring clear and collective political, social, cultural, and pedagogical guidelines. One of the central roles of the PP is to promote inclusive education, establishing strategies that value diversity and contribute to overcoming learning barriers. Inclusion goes beyond curriculum adaptation, encompassing the construction of a welcoming and equitable environment that respects differences and enables active student participation. The research conducted at Escola MDA, with semi-structured interviews with educational managers, highlighted the importance of the PP in organizing school practices. However, challenges were identified regarding the awareness and involvement of the school community in the effective use of this document. Although recognized as an essential guide, the PP is not widely appropriated by teachers, students, and the school community, which limits its practical application. To address this issue, the research pointed out ways to strengthen the engagement of the school community, highlighting the need for greater awareness about the importance of the PP. Actions such as periodic meetings, continuous training, and dialogue spaces can make the document more present in everyday school life. Furthermore, the use of participatory evaluations in its review can broaden the involvement of everyone, ensuring that the PP is a dynamic element aligned with the real needs of the school. It is concluded that the effectiveness of the Pedagogical Project depends on the articulation between different educational agents, promoting a space of collective learning and commitment to inclusion and the quality of education.

Keywords: Pedagogical Project, Collective Participation, School Inclusion, Participatory Evaluation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The school's Pedagogical Project (PP) guides the educational process, articulating the collective needs and desires of the school community with broader educational perspectives. Its development and updating are essential to strengthen the school's identity and autonomy, aligning it with current legislation and social transformation projects that span the field of education, without losing sight of reality and collectively reconstructed goals. This process must also consider the guidelines and perspectives of educational policies at the municipal and state levels, establishing connections between local demands and the broader objectives of public education.

This study is justified by the need to deepen the understanding of how collective participation in the construction of the PP can contribute to the consolidation of democratic management in public schools, especially in contexts where diversity and inclusion must be prioritized. Understanding the challenges and possibilities of this participation is essential to strengthen the articulation between the school and the community, as well as to ensure that pedagogical planning takes into account the different voices that make up the school universe.

The importance of PP lies in its ability to structure and direct educational practice, promoting an inclusive and reflective school environment. The teacher's actions must enable the collective construction of knowledge, anchored in the culture of the school community itself. To this end, it is essential to create interactive and dialogical spaces, where educators and students share ideas and experiences, stimulating critical reflection and the development of autonomy.

Schools must be recognized as socio-political and educational spaces that are essential for building citizenship, and this responsibility cannot fall exclusively on teachers. A solid foundation is needed, involving school management, the educational community and the social environment, strengthening collective participation in the construction of the pedagogical project.

The problem is defined by analyzing the process of constructing the PP, investigating with educational managers whether there are spaces and to what extent the school community is involved in the elaboration and review of the project. Collective participation ensures that different perspectives are taken into account, resulting in a project that reflects the diversity and needs of the school community. This approach strengthens the commitment to a democratic school, where the plurality of voices guides decisions and pedagogical practices.

2. THEORETICAL BASIS

2.1. The Pedagogical Project as a systematization of school work

The Pedagogical Project (PP) is one of the most relevant instruments adopted by state and municipal education departments, as highlighted by Riscal (2009). Its development is based on Article 12 of the LDB, which determines that it is the school's responsibility to construct its own pedagogical project. Articles 13 and 14 expand this responsibility, establishing the active participation of teachers, other education professionals, school and local communities, through school councils or equivalent bodies.

The construction of the PP must involve managers, teachers, students and families, promoting democratic management that strengthens the school identity and ensures that the decisions made represent the community. This participatory process encourages engagement and commitment to the implementation of the project (Eça & Coelho, 2021).

Vasconcelos (2004) emphasizes that community participation in the development of the pedagogical project creates a more collaborative and efficient educational environment, aligning the document with the real needs of the school and students. The inclusion of different voices in the process makes the project more representative and adapted to the specificities of the school context.

Democratic management is one of the fundamental pillars, encouraging dialogue, shared decision-making and the collective construction of knowledge. This model strengthens school identity, generates a sense of belonging and values the culture and values of the institution, creating a welcoming environment conducive to learning.

The main functions of the PP include:

- **Define guidelines and objectives:** establishing educational goals aligned with the reality and specific needs of the school.
- **Guide pedagogical practice:** organizing teaching and learning strategies in a cohesive manner and aligned with the adopted educational principles.
- **Promote democratic management :** ensuring the active participation of the school community in the construction and review of institutional guidelines.
- **Ensure inclusion and diversity:** considering the cultural, social and economic plurality of the school community, ensuring an equitable and accessible education for all.
- **Evaluate and improve school practice:** enabling continuous monitoring of the actions developed and making adjustments to improve the educational process.

As a management tool, the pedagogical project guides the distribution of resources, the organization of time and school space, the ongoing training of teachers and the promotion of an environment that favors learning, collaboration, well-being and the integral development of students. It also directs institutional evaluation and the monitoring of educational indicators.

The participation of the school community in the development and review of the project is essential to its effectiveness. Collective involvement allows for the consideration of different perspectives, strengthening the bond between school and community and increasing the sense of belonging and shared responsibility in the construction of the educational project.

Participatory evaluation transforms the planning and review of the PP into a political and democratic process. Students, teachers and community members actively collaborate in defining criteria, collecting and analyzing data, ensuring that the project reflects the diverse needs of the school community. This approach promotes dialogue, strengthens collective construction and ensures a dynamic, updated project adapted to the demands of the school.

2.2 Normative aspects and educational guidelines

Brazilian educational guidelines establish fundamental parameters for the construction of the Pedagogical Project. Resolution CNE/CEB No. 5/2009 defines the National Curricular Guidelines for Early Childhood Education, while Resolutions CNE/CEB No. 7/2010 and CNE/CEB No. 2/2012 establish guidelines for elementary and secondary education. Law No. 12,796/2013 reinforces the importance of training education professionals, and the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) guides the development of essential skills for students (BRASIL, 2013).

The relationship between the PP and educational legislation is essential to ensure the application of national guidelines in pedagogical practice. The Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education (LDB - Law No. 9,394/1996) establishes principles such as democratic management, pedagogical autonomy and appreciation of the education professional. According to Goulart (2012, p. 47), the “Pedagogical Project must be constructed in a participatory manner, ensuring the collaboration of managers, teachers, students and the entire school community, allowing the school to meet its local specificities without losing sight of national references”.

The BNCC (BRAZIL, 2018) highlights the need for education focused on developing skills and abilities for citizenship and the world of work. The PP must contemplate interdisciplinarity, the comprehensive education of students and educational inclusion, ensuring

equity and diversity in the school environment. Goulart (2012) emphasizes that democratic educational practices must respect differences and promote citizenship education based on social justice and the active participation of students.

The pedagogical project must be aligned with the ethical, political and pedagogical principles established by educational legislation. In ethical terms, education must promote values such as respect, responsibility, solidarity and social justice. For Goulart (2012), democratic management favors the collective construction of knowledge and respect for diversity, making the school environment more inclusive.

In the political sphere, the PP must consolidate democracy, encouraging active student participation through practices that promote critical reflection and student leadership. Democratic management transforms school subjects into active agents in the construction of knowledge, strengthening the school's identity and the culture of cooperation (Goulart, 2012).

In this context, the organization of the Pedagogical Project must include aspects that guarantee collective participation and the construction of actions aligned with the needs and specificities of the school community. Below, we point out the main elements that can guide the elaboration of the PP, according to Riscal (2009), considering its democratic and inclusive nature.

Table 1: Elements for Building the Pedagogical Project (PP)

1. Justification	Presentation of the concepts and pedagogical guidelines that guide the project, including the history of the school, organization, available resources and profile of the school community.
2. Justification	Description of the school reality, highlighting the main problems and challenges.
3. Diagnosis	Collective reflection and survey of indicators to understand the school's needs.
4. Goals	Definition of clear and achievable objectives based on the indicators collected.
5. General Objectives	Final results expected with the implementation of the project.
6. Specific Objectives	Detailed actions to achieve the proposed goals.
7. Action Plan	Definition of those responsible, deadlines, costs and resources required to carry out the actions.
8. Evaluation	Strategies for monitoring and continuous review of the project at each stage.

Source: adaptation by Riscal (2009)

This table provides a suggestion for the school to develop its own itinerary to be followed, according to its specificities.

2.3 Participatory assessment in the Pedagogical Project

Participatory evaluation, from the pragmatic perspective addressed in this article, is understood as a process that aims to guarantee and expand the use of results to improve educational effectiveness, as highlighted by Furtado (2012). This approach is linked to the principles of democratic management, by integrating the active participation of the school community as a central element for the construction of collective autonomy and for the strengthening of inclusive practices.

The participation of the school community in the development of the pedagogical project is essential not only for defining the institution's objectives and guidelines, but also for monitoring and continuously reviewing results and goals, ensuring that the established purposes are constantly reassessed and adjusted to the school's needs. This participatory process strengthens the bond between the school and the community, promoting a culture of co-responsibility and belonging.

As Furtado (2012, p. 26) highlights,

"This is a participation that goes far beyond the provision of information, and may involve different actors in some or all stages of the evaluation (such as defining questions, collecting and analyzing data, judging and formulating recommendations)." This approach broadens the understanding of evaluation as a collective and continuous process, capable of improving the quality of education.

To this end, school management, in the form of the director and pedagogical coordinator, must assume the role of facilitator and partner, with the expectation that the process of constructing the PP "will enable the assimilation, by participants, of skills to understand and use future results, as well as to get involved and conduct new assessments" (idem).

In preparing the PP, each segment plays a fundamental role:

- **Managers:** coordinate and facilitate the process, ensuring transparency and encouraging active participation from everyone involved.
- **Teachers:** share their pedagogical experiences and knowledge about students' needs, aligning educational practices with institutional objectives.

- **Students** : contribute with their perspectives, ensuring that the PP takes into account their needs and interests, making the school more dynamic and inclusive.
- **Families**: strengthen the bond between school and community, promoting a collaborative and participatory environment.

The implementation of participation mechanisms, such as school assemblies, class councils and public consultations, makes the construction of the PP a continuous and dynamic process, ensuring that the document remains up to date and aligned with the educational needs of the community.

The participatory evaluation of the PP should involve all segments of the school community, using strategies such as pedagogical meetings, study groups and opinion polls. However, this process should not be restricted to planning and execution, but should also include the evaluation of the choices and resulting impacts, consolidating a practice of critical reflection and constant improvement.

According to Eça and Coelho (2021), participatory evaluation allows the PP to remain up to date and adapted to the school's needs. Resolution CNE/CEB No. 2/2012 also emphasizes that the participation of all school segments in the PP evaluation contributes to strengthening institutional identity and planning.

The collaborative work of the school team, made up of managers, teachers, pedagogical coordinators and other education professionals, encourages a plurality of ideas and experiences, enriching pedagogical planning. Active listening and dialogue among members of the school community strengthen institutional identity and improve the quality of education offered.

To promote effective engagement of educators in the participatory evaluation of PP, the following strategies can be adopted:

- **Periodic Pedagogical Meetings**: regular meetings to discuss challenges and improvements to the PP, encouraging collaboration and collective learning.
- **Continuing Education**: courses, lectures and workshops to update educators on new educational guidelines and innovative methodologies.
- **Thematic Working Groups**: teams focused on specific aspects of the PP, such as inclusion, active methodologies and learning assessment.
- **Participatory Research and Consultations**: questionnaires and interactive dynamics that allow school professionals to express their opinions.
- **School Councils and Assemblies**: spaces for collective deliberation where the entire school community can contribute with proposals and constructive criticism.

The participatory evaluation of the PP has a direct impact on promoting inclusion and adapting pedagogical practices to the school's needs. The involvement of the school community makes the PP more flexible and responsive to the demands of students, especially those in vulnerable situations or with special educational needs.

The inclusion of continuous assessment mechanisms allows for agile adjustments, ensuring more equitable and quality education. Thus, the PP becomes a living, dynamic document that represents the school reality, consolidating democratic management and the collective construction of the educational project.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research will be supported by the qualitative approach which, according to Riscal (2009), seeks to understand the meanings attributed by the participants to the phenomena studied, allowing an in-depth analysis of the educational processes in their natural context and valuing the perceptions of the subjects involved.

The MDA School was chosen as the field of study because it is part of the daily life of one of the researchers, facilitating a deeper immersion in the institutional reality. In addition, the school stands out in the municipality for developing innovative pedagogical practices and for its continuous search for the implementation of a participatory Pedagogical Project. According to Riscal (2009), institutions that promote democratic management and collective participation in the elaboration of their pedagogical projects tend to strengthen their institutional identity and promote more inclusive and democratic teaching.

The MDA School is located in an industrial area and serves elementary school students in the early and late years, divided into two shifts: morning and afternoon. In the morning shift, students from 1st to 5th grade are served; in the afternoon, students from 6th to 9th grade are served. Students with specific educational needs are served outside of regular school hours in the AEE resource room at another school unit, since the school does not have an AEE room.

The choice to use interviews was made because they were appropriate for the purposes of this research, allowing the interviewees to express their perceptions, experiences and suggestions about the process of constructing the PP, investigating whether there are spaces and to what extent the school community is involved in the process of elaborating and reviewing the project. The participants are four managers who work at this school.

The collected data were analyzed using the content analysis technique, following the steps of coding, categorization and interpretation (Bardin 2011). This approach allows the

identification of patterns and relationships between the interviewees' responses, enabling a broader understanding.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The research included the participation of four managers from the MDA School, who answered two open questions with the aim of reflecting on the materialization of the Pedagogical Project (PP), considering democratic management and its role in the inclusive perspective.

Questions:

1) In your opinion, what are the biggest difficulties in involving the school community (teachers, staff, parents and students) in the discussion, preparation and implementation of the Pedagogical Project at the school?

2) Based on your experience, what is the role of the Pedagogical Project in school inclusion?

Data analysis was performed based on the content analysis technique proposed by Bardin (2011), which enabled the coding, categorization and interpretation of responses. This method allowed the identification of patterns and relationships between the managers' perceptions, deepening the understanding of the challenges and strategies for implementing the PP.

The pre-analysis and exploration stages of the material resulted in the definition of three categories: a) definition of roles, b) involvement of the school community, and c) educational inclusion.

4.1 Main Challenges in Implementing the PP

The analysis revealed four main challenges for implementing the PP, as highlighted in Figure 1:

Image 1 - Challenges in Implementing the PP

Source: AI-generated image on Napkin

Time Limitations challenge refers to the lack of time for collaborative planning, development, review and updating, considering the engagement of the entire school community. This limitation prevents the PP from being developed efficiently and aligned with the school's needs.

Understanding **Roles** corresponds to the lack of clarity about the functions performed by the different members of the school community in the preparation of the PP, which compromises effective participation and the collective construction of the document.

Professional Turnover addresses the constant change of teachers and managers in the school staff, making it difficult to continue and consolidate the PP, since the frequent change of agents interferes with institutional memory and the execution of planning.

Low Participation highlights the insufficient involvement of the school community in discussions and activities related to the PP, which weakens its effectiveness as an instrument guiding pedagogical practices.

To contextualize the managers' responses, the Municipal Department of Education guides and evaluates the schools' pedagogical project in regular four-year cycles, a period used as a reference for the development and continuous adjustments of the document by the school.

The difficulties identified highlight the need for actions that encourage the active participation of the school community in all stages of the process. The school, the family and the student must be recognized as interconnected elements that work together to consolidate the PP as a guiding instrument for pedagogical actions. In addition to offering emotional and structural support for the development of students, the family contributes to the construction of

educational paths aligned with individual needs. The school is configured as a space for learning and development, where teachers, students and the community interact to promote knowledge and citizenship. The student occupies the center of the educational structure, assuming the role of protagonist in the learning process itself. This continuous interaction strengthens the collective construction of the PP, promoting a more inclusive education aligned with the needs of the community.

It is therefore essential to invest in strategies that ensure greater clarity of functions and encourage collective engagement. Managers emphasize that the PP must establish clear guidelines to ensure an inclusive school. Collective participation, as pointed out by Riscal (2009) and Goulart (2012), is essential to promote efficient school management that is committed to the quality of education. Active listening to the school community and coordination between different sectors are fundamental measures to transform the PP into an effective instrument, capable of meeting the needs of the school and society.

4.2 Strategies to Improve PP Appropriation

To overcome the challenges mentioned, the research participants suggested strategic actions, represented in the following image. The arrangement of the image, organized from the base to the top of the ladder, reflects the progressive construction of the appropriation of the PP:

Image 2 - Strategies to improve PP appropriation

Source: AI-generated image on Napkin

Regular School Meetings , the first step, highlight the need for periodic meetings to discuss, evaluate and promote collective understanding about the PP, ensuring the active participation of all segments of the school community.

Family Involvement , the second step, highlights the importance of the partnership between school and family, increasing parental participation in monitoring school development and in the construction of pedagogical strategies.

The **Support of the Education Department** , the third step, proposes the creation of institutional spaces for planning and training professionals, favoring more coherent and effective action in the execution of the PP.

At the top of the ladder, **Community-School Integration** crowns the collective construction, stimulating interaction between teachers, managers, students, families and other members of the community, consolidating the PP as a guiding instrument for pedagogical practices and democratic management.

The analysis of the responses reveals that these actions, if implemented efficiently, can generate greater engagement and understanding of the importance of the PP in the pedagogical organization of the school. The categorization of the managers' statements shows that the lack of clarity about how to act and the low participation of the school community are central challenges for the appropriation of the PP.

In this context, it is essential to promote regular meetings that include all sectors of the school community, ensuring institutionalized time for planning, reflection and active listening. As Riscal (2009) highlights, democratic management requires processes of collective participation in decision-making, reinforcing the need for permanent dialogic spaces in the school.

Goulart (2012) emphasizes that a collectively constructed PP promotes organization, systematization and continuous evaluation of school work. Strengthening democratic management and creating participatory strategies make the PP a dynamic and inclusive instrument, reflecting educational reality and incorporating different voices in pedagogical planning.

Therefore, when considering the strategies suggested by managers and the literature on democratic management, it is clear that the success of implementing the PP depends on building a collaborative school environment, where the active participation of all those involved is guaranteed and encouraged.

4.3 The Role of the Pedagogical Project in School Inclusion

When addressing school inclusion, the Pedagogical Project is essential to ensure equitable and accessible education for all. The qualitative analysis of pedagogical practices allowed us to identify challenges and propose solutions to make the school environment more inclusive. The image below illustrates the main aspects that the PP should contemplate to promote inclusion:

Image 3 - Implementation of PP for inclusion

Source: AI-generated image on Napkin

Democratic Openness emphasizes the inclusion of the entire school community in the development and review of the PP, ensuring that different perspectives are considered. This collective process strengthens democratic governance and ensures that the needs of the school community are addressed.

The **Definition of Responsibilities** understands the need for greater clarity in the role of each actor in the implementation of school inclusion. Well-defined guidelines ensure that teachers, families, support professionals and administrators know how to act to promote an accessible and welcoming environment.

Inclusive Action Planning includes pedagogical strategies that promote inclusion, such as curricular adaptation, the use of assistive technologies and diversified methodological practices. The development of continuing education programs for teachers is also a crucial factor in consolidating inclusion in schools.

Continuous Review shows that school inclusion requires a process of constant evaluation of the PP, allowing adjustments and improvements according to the needs of students and the institution. This monitoring ensures that inclusive practices are effective and aligned with educational guidelines.

Riscal (2009) and Goulart (2012) emphasize that democratic management is essential for the PP to become a living and active document, capable of guiding pedagogical practices in an inclusive manner. Collective construction ensures coherence between the needs of the school community and educational guidelines. The analysis of the perceptions of managers revealed that effective inclusion depends on collaboration between schools, families, the health sector and public authorities, enabling more structured support for students and promoting teaching that respects diversity.

The study shows that the PP must establish concrete strategies and clearly define those responsible for their implementation. Active listening to the school community and coordination between different sectors are fundamental measures to transform the PP into a dynamic and effective instrument. As the authors point out, collective participation strengthens school management, making it more efficient and committed to the quality of education.

By ensuring the continuous review of the PP and fostering a democratic approach in its construction, the school moves closer to a more equitable educational model. Strengthening inclusive strategies and clearly defining responsibilities consolidate the PP as a central element in ensuring that no student is excluded from the educational process.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The Pedagogical Project plays a strategic role in promoting inclusion and educational quality, guiding the organization of pedagogical work. Its alignment with educational guidelines ensures that the school curriculum meets legal requirements and the contemporary needs of students, favoring a comprehensive and contextualized education.

The study showed that low participation by the school community is one of the main challenges to the effective implementation of the PP, aggravated by the high turnover of professionals and the lack of understanding of the roles of each actor in the educational process. This reality highlights the importance of democratic management that values collective engagement in the construction and continuous review of the project. Municipal education departments have sought to encourage this participation by offering materials and support to schools, covering the main structural elements of the PP.

However, the support of democratic management alone does not guarantee the active participation of all those involved. Strengthening the engagement of managers, teachers, staff, students and families is essential to consolidate the collective construction of the document. In

this sense, Furtado (2012) proposes questions that should guide management in promoting more effective participation, such as:

- How to share technical decisions, expanding participation beyond management, and offering support so that everyone feels able to contribute?
- How to define the most relevant participants for the construction of the document, considering resources, available time and feasibility of involvement?
- What weight will each group have in formulating recommendations, with managers acting as mediators without minimizing the responsibilities of each segment?
- How to manage unforeseen events with flexibility and firmness, avoiding process interruption?
- How to establish the depth of community participation in the different phases of the process, from the formulation of questions to the analysis and judgment of data?

Based on these reflections, an initial movement is proposed that seeks to understand the school context and its community before planning the PP. This process can be based on the structure presented in Table 3:

Table 2: Suggestion for preparing the PP

Diagnosis and Characterization of the Community	General objectives	Goals (specific objectives)	Actions Methods/ duration	Cost	Responsible	Items for evaluation
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Source: Adapted from Riscal (2009, p.107)

Clearly defining objectives, goals and pedagogical strategies should consider not only the cognitive aspects, but also the emotional, social and cultural aspects of students. Strategies such as regular meetings, active listening, community awareness and greater coordination between school, family and institutional sectors are essential to increase engagement and ensure a more participatory and efficient PP.

To strengthen inclusion and community involvement, it is recommended to implement practices that promote the protagonism of different school segments. The creation of permanent spaces for debate, ongoing training for educators, and the holding of institutional moments aimed at the collective construction of the document are actions that consolidate democratic participation. Participatory evaluation emerges as an essential tool for the continuous improvement of the PP, allowing adjustments based on the school's reality and the students' needs.

Therefore, the PP not only structures the school's pedagogical organization, but is also a transformative instrument capable of promoting equitable and socially responsible education. Its continuous improvement, based on collective participation and democratic management, is essential to guarantee the right to learning for all students.

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